

Actively Teaching the Teachers: Impact of a Professional Development Initiative for Early Career Staff in Higher Education

Tom O'Mahony¹, Sinead Huskisson², William Carey³

¹ Teaching and Learning Unit, Munster Technological University, Cork, Ireland. ORCID 0000-0002-0658-5797

² Department of Management & Enterprise, Munster Technological University, Cork, Ireland. ORCID 0000-0002-0962-9951

³ Senior Educational Developer, Nottingham Trent University, Nottingham, UK.

Email: tom.omahony@mt.ie, sinead.huskisson@mtu.ie, william.carey@ntu.ac.uk.

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Abstract

EAT-PD (Enabling Academic Transitions through Professional Development) is an innovative initiative that addresses a critical need in higher education: developing the teaching practices of early-career faculty to promote active, collaborative and inclusive teaching strategies. This one semester long, one hour per week, online, synchronous program introduces early-career faculty to active learning strategies through modelling these strategies. Example strategies include classroom-response systems, discussions, peer-instruction, flipped classroom and team-based learning. While large-scale classroom observation studies continue to establish the need for instructional development programs within higher education, the impact of existing programs on classroom practices is contested. Therefore, this article contributes by adopting a quasi-experimental pre-test/post-test design to evaluate the impact of the EAT-PD program on the instructional practices of participants. Participants completed a pre-survey (n=51) and post-survey (n=34) which explored the frequency of use of specific teaching strategies during that time-period. Pre and post responses showed a statistically significant difference for questions relating to the frequency with which participants put students into pairs or small groups for extended time periods during class and for the question related to soliciting student feedback. Additionally, content analysis was used to code responses to a mid-semester survey (n=49). This data revealed that experiencing active learning strategies within a peer-supported environment were keys to the success of the EAT-PD instructional development initiative. Future research will explore long-term impacts on teaching practice and student outcomes.

Keywords: Active Learning; early career faculty; instructional development; quasi-experimental design.

1 Introduction

A substantial body of evidence demonstrates that active learning positively impacts student learning and student outcomes for all learners (Freeman et al., 2014; Theobald et al., 2020). However, evidence from classroom observations suggest that traditional lectures continue to dominate higher education practice (Noben et al., 2022; Stains et al., 2018). As many academics enter teaching roles with limited pedagogical training, supporting early-career faculty to adopt active and evidence-based practices is critical to fostering long-term instructional excellence in higher education. Enabling Academic Transitions through Professional Development (EAT-PD) is an instructional development program for early-career Lecturers at Munster Technological University (MTU), Cork Ireland. To the authors' knowledge this initiative, with its focus on active learning for early-career faculty, is unique in the Higher Education sector in Ireland. Internationally, the impact of active learning instructional development initiatives on the actual classroom practices of higher education faculty is contested (Emery et al., 2020; Schmid et al., 2021). This article contributes by adopting a quasi-experimental pre-test/post-test design to evaluate the impact of a one-semester, online instructional development program that aims to support early-career faculty to adopt active learning instructional approaches. In doing so it establishes the link between instructional development and impact on teaching practices. This link is critically important as institutions aim to improve teaching effectiveness and support

academic transitions. Of equal importance is the need to evaluate the measurable impacts of instructional development programs and justify the resources invested in faculty development.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Active Learning

Active Learning can be defined as ‘a classroom situation in which the instructor and instructional activities explicitly afford students’ agency in learning’ (Lombardi et al., 2021, p. 15). A convincing body of research demonstrates the efficacy of active learning. For example, the meta-analysis conducted by Freeman et al. (2014) evidenced that active learning positively impacts learning achievement and reduces failure rates. This impact extends from Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics disciplines (Freeman et al., 2014) through to humanities and social science disciplines (Kozanitis & Nenciovici, 2023). Active learning has also been shown to reduce achievement gaps associated with underrepresented students (Theobald et al., 2020). Hence, ideas traditionally associated with active learning e.g. engagement and collaboration are increasingly prioritised in strategies designed to support equity and diversity, such as universal design for learning (Moriña et al., 2025).

However, despite this convincing body of evidence in favor of active learning as a pedagogy, the majority of faculty continue to use the more traditional lecture format in their own classrooms. For example, the large scale observation study conducted by Stains et al. (2018) revealed that lecture-based approaches are more common than active learning. A more recent study, consisting of 203 classroom observations, concluded that it was ‘striking that almost half of the observed lecturers did not demonstrate sufficient activating teaching behavior since the importance of active learning for student achievement has been well-established in higher education’ (Noben et al., 2022, p. 39). The authors also observed that while ‘lecturers might have the required knowledge related to these domains, they often struggle with implementing this knowledge into practice’ (Noben et al., 2022, p. 39). Studies exploring the integration of technology and assessment practices have arrived at similar conclusions – that traditional, instructor-centred practices dominate (Lillejord et al., 2018; Myers & Myers, 2015).

2.2 Faculty Implementation of Active Learning

Consequently, instructional developers have designed various initiatives to encourage faculty to adopt active learning pedagogies. Some of these initiatives have targeted early-career faculty, due to the recognition of substantial impact that initial teaching experiences can have on the personal and professional lives of academics (Feixas, 2002). One such initiative, the US-based Faculty Institutes for Reforming Science Teaching (FIRST) IV program, was aimed at biology postdoctoral researchers and ran from 2009 to 2013 (Emery et al., 2020). FIRST IV was a two-year program that focused on curriculum development and mentored teaching practicums. Over the course of the program, FIRST IV participants learned about and applied instructional strategies to engage students in learning the core biological concepts. Rigorous evaluations included teaching observations of FIRST IV participants compared with paired faculty i.e. faculty with a similar profile from the same department but had not participated in FIRST IV. FIRST IV participants demonstrated greater levels of active student engagement and implemented more learner-centered classrooms than their peers and this change persisted long after (6 to 9 years) participation in FIRST IV (Emery et al., 2020). Viskupic et al. (2019, p. 201) also used classroom observations and report that ‘that instructors with at least 24 h of PD are significantly more likely to teach a Student-Centered class than instructors with fewer hours’ and that those odds increase if the instructional development undertaken is discipline-specific. Meizlish et al. (2018) drew on student course evaluations to explore the impact on faculty who had undertaken instructional development relative to a

control group. Their data demonstrated statistically significant positive effects in relation to overall course ratings, instructor ratings and self-reported learning gains.

Findings from other studies reveal the contested impact of instructional development programs. Evaluations of instructional development initiatives undertaken in Belgium, China and the US evidenced a positive impact on self-efficacy and conceptions of teaching but little impact on teaching behavior and no improvement in student learning (Favre et al., 2021; Greer et al., 2021; Stes & Van Petegem, 2011). Using a quasi-experimental design that explored impact based on course design and classroom observations, Schmid et al. (2021) report that early-career participants performed similarly to the control group that did not participate in instructional development. Gebru (2016, p. 1741) observed that their early-career participants' 'teaching practice still largely draws from their previous teachers' indicating that the instructional development program was not fully effective. Ross et al. (2020) explored the impact of a two-year instructional development program on engineering faculty in the US. While classroom observations indicated 'positive shifts in active learning strategies in the classroom' the overall analysis suggested that participating in the program did not impact student achievement (Ross et al., 2020, p. 14).

So, despite the convincing evidence in favor of active learning pedagogies, the majority of faculty persist with more traditional lecture-based formats (Noben et al., 2022; Stains et al., 2018). This persistence points to the need for instructional development that aims to transform classroom-based practices. Focusing on early-career academics is advantageous due to their potential longevity within the university system and they key role that those initial years play in building academics' identity, socialization and practice (Feixas, 2002; Kelchtermans, 2019). The neo-liberal agenda and tight budgets within with many universities operate, places an increasing demand to establish the efficacy of instructional development initiatives and to evidence that investment in instructional development has been worthwhile. This study contributes by establishing the link between early-career participation in an instructional development program and changes in teaching practice.

3 Research Method

The research question addressed by this study is:

- (1) To what extent does participation in the EAT-PD program increase instructors' use of active learning strategies within their own classrooms?

3.1 EAT-PD Instructional Development Program

The EAT-PD Instructional Development program targets early career faculty³ at MTU. The aim of the EAT-PD initiative is to challenge traditional conceptions of teaching and encouraging the adoption of active and collaborative instructional approaches. EAT-PD is a 12-week long program that is delivered on-line using a mixture of weekly 1-hour synchronous sessions and recommended resources hosted on a Learning Management System platform. The initiative focuses on discussing and modelling active learning strategies including the use of interactive polling tools, think-pair-share, small group discussions, peer-instruction, team-based learning and the flipped classroom. The initiative also highlights how active learning is inclusive and effectively reduces the achievement gap associated with underrepresented students in higher education (Theobald et al., 2020). As outputs, participants are asked to develop a Module Enhancement Plan which outlines how active learning strategies could be used to solve a teaching and learning challenge participants are experiencing and develop a 1,400 word reflective account of practice to meet the requirements for Associate Fellowship of Advance HE (*Associate Fellowship*, 2025). Advance HE is a UK-based charity that aims

³ At MTU early-career is defined as faculty employed by the university for three years or less in a full-time or part-time capacity

to improve higher education for staff, students and society. Fellowships are awarded based on evidence that personal practice meets the requirements of the teaching and learning standards framework for the higher education section (Advance HE, 2023).

3.2 Research Approach

The study adopts a mixed-methods approach combining a quasi-experimental pre-test/post-test design to measure changes in participants' reported practices along with an open-ended survey to explore their experiences of the EAT-PD instructional development program. The use of pre- and post-surveys enables assessment of effectiveness by comparing baseline and post-intervention practices, and allows for a statistical analysis of change over time. The pre-test survey was administered during the first meeting with each cohort, the post-test was administered during the last meeting with each cohort while the open-ended survey was administered mid-way through the initiative. All data was collected via anonymous online instruments.

3.3 Participants

The authors ran the EAT-PD program in January - June 2020, Sept. – Dec 2020, January – June 2021, January – June 2024 and Sept. – Dec 2024. A colleague ran the program in the intervening years 2021 and 2024 but data was not collected. Over these five semesters 85 early-career faculty participated in the program. 51 participants responded to the pre-survey instrument, 34 to the post-survey and 49 participants responded to the open-ended mid-semester survey.

3.4 Data Analysis

As the quantitative pre- and post-survey data was collected anonymously and have unequal sample sizes, it was not possible to pair responses. Consequently, following Levene's test to establish equal variance, a two-sample (Independent) t-test with equal variances was used to statistically analyze the responses. Open ended responses were inductively coded. A descriptive coding approach was adopted as Saldaña (2021) advises that descriptive codes are useful for capturing 'what is talked about'. The frequency with which these codes appeared in the data was then counted to get a sense of the relative importance of the various experiences represented in the data.

4 Findings

Table 1 presents a statistical analysis of the pre- and post-survey results with the Likert *scale* never being mapped to 0 and *every class* being mapped to 4. This analysis reveals that statistically significant results were found for two questions. Participants reported that, subsequent to the EAT-PD intervention, they were more likely to implement small group, collaborative learning approaches for MOST of the class period and more likely to solicit student feedback to enhance their own teaching practice ($p < 0.01$). The question asking whether participants assigned more out-of-class work to individuals subsequent to participating in the instructional development intervention was almost statistically significant at the 5% level ($p = 0.059$).

Table 1: Statistical analysis of the pre- and post-survey items using a two-sample (Independent) t-test with equal variances

Survey Question	Average			p-value
	Pre	Post	Post-Pre	
Q5. How often do you lecture for most of the class period?	3.13	2.91	-0.22	0.252
Q6. How often do you use demonstrations in class (live or multimedia)?	2.83	2.82	-0.01	0.985
Q7. How often do you address questions to the class as a whole?	3.56	3.56	0.00	0.995

Q8. How often do you put students into pairs or small groups for brief intervals during class to answer questions, solve problems or discuss concepts/issues?	2.31	2.53	0.22	0.272
Q9. How often do you put students into pairs or small groups for MOST of a class period to answer questions, solve problems or discuss an issue?	1.58	2.09	0.51	0.004**
Q10. How often do you assign homework (out of class work) to individuals (as opposed to teams)?	2.08	2.5	0.42	0.059*
Q11. How often do you give students the option of working in teams (2 or more) to complete homework or assignments?	1.54	1.62	0.08	0.625
Q12. How often do you give a writing assignment (any exercise that requires explanations and not just calculations)?	1.92	2.18	0.26	0.119
Q14. Have you solicited student feedback for the purpose of improving your teaching during the last semester?	0.60	0.88	0.28	0.002**

** significant at the 1% level ($p < 0.001$); * almost significant at the 5% level ($p < 0.05$)

Table 2 presents the findings from the qualitative analysis. The first column presents the descriptive codes that were derived from responses to the open-ended question, the second column presents the frequency with which these codes appeared in the data while the final column presents representative quotes from participants. Table 2 evidences that direct exposure to active learning and experiencing the benefits associated with peer-learning positively impacted participants as did learning about active learning and specific active learning strategies. Participants praised the EAT-PD instructional development program, finding it useful and enjoyable and, to a lesser extent, that it positively impacted confidence levels. In relation to enhancing EAT-PD, participants suggested that sharing more resources on active learning and more specific examples of how active learning strategies have been implemented by faculty in different disciplines would be useful.

Table 2: Qualitative analysis of the open-ended mid-semester survey data

Code	Freq.	Representative Quotes from Participants
Peer learning	32	'The group workshops and the fact that we are able to develop and share ideas with our peers before reflecting them back to the class group. I find this an effective way to learn' 'The open discussion forum whereby you can learn from the experience of others. It helps you realise that other lecturers face the same issues and challenges' 'Hearing other peoples' perspectives' 'I find having a cohort of fellow lecturers from different departments is very useful as we can learn how different teaching principles can be applied across disciplines'
Active learning	26	'Learning about active teaching methods - looking at the research, examples and case studies' 'The opportunity to explore different types of active learning' 'Some of the practical techniques and approaches around reinforcing learning, peer learning and group discussions in class etc I have already applied with some success, I hope!'
Useful	18	'I am benefiting and learning a lot from these classes' 'All of the techniques are simple and very practical and could be adopted immediately in my current teaching practice'
Enjoyable	14	'I am really enjoying the course and I know it has already improved my teaching skills, I have been able to apply some of the strategies to the (virtual) classroom' 'I am enjoying the course immensely'

Course content	11	'The content is generally very informative and interesting' 'The carefully curated reading material and research given on the course gives me the direction to focus on important areas to promote a better teaching environment'
Praise	11	'Great initiative, it is really informative' 'I think the program has been brilliant thus far without any real limitations'
Specific examples	8	'I find it very helpful when more experienced lectures share tools they use successfully in their classes. More of these discussions would be great' 'Maybe more insights from other peoples' experiences from teaching, what worked well and what didn't work well, insight from people who had to deal with poor class attendance'
More resources	8	'In general, some more literature would be beneficial I think' 'More online resources for self-study on teaching practices and methods'
Confidence	6	'It has given me a newfound confidence in not just my teaching but in all my dealings at MTU' 'I am really enjoying this module and finding that it is greatly improving my confidence in the classroom'

5 Discussion

Research on faculty instructional development reveals that initiatives that are active and longer duration are more impactful (Stes & Van Petegem, 2011; Viskupic et al., 2019). Aligning with the literature on learning in general (Freeman et al., 2014; Weimer, 2013), the literature on instructional development identifies the impact of collaborative approaches where faculty share and learn from each other (Dancy et al., 2016; Desimone, 2009). This evidence base informed the design of the EAT-PD initiative and the decisions that it should run over one semester and that the initiative would focus on modelling active learning strategies so that participants could experience the benefits of peer-learning. The qualitative data suggests that experiencing active learning first-hand was important in supporting participants to develop their instructional practices. Participants frequently mentioned the usefulness of small group discussions e.g. 'tasks where we were given something to read and discuss together in break out rooms have been helpful' and 'we are able to develop and share ideas with our peers before reflecting them back to the class group. I find this an effective way to learn'. Participants also highlighted how they learnt from peers. Hearing about the 'challenges experienced by other colleagues' and learning 'different techniques to address these' was highly valued by participants. This sharing of experiences helped normalize challenges for these early-career faculty and provided a supportive environment for exploring perspectives and ideas. Consequently, participants report that they found 'the active learning [in] small groups', 'shared learning between peers in class' and 'learning from others' very beneficial. In the words of one participant 'my own experience as a student on this program has shown me that groupwork is hugely valuable'. Consequently, we contend that this practical experience of collaborative learning and peer dialogue — where staff could share challenges, strategies, and build confidence *together* — helps explain why EAT-PD was impactful in supporting participants to enhance their own classroom practices.

Additionally, participants highlighted how EAT-PD provided them with the direct exposure to active learning as a pedagogy along with practical strategies, tools and concrete examples that could be easily implemented or transferred into their teaching practices. The program helped participants to understand that 'lecturing is not an effective means of learning' and 'to reduce the content I am delivering' to 'ensure that students are learning'. Participants highlighted simple but practical strategies such as breaking hour-long classes into '12min lecture, activity, 12min lecture, etc'. Participants reported that there was a good balance between 'the general benefits of active learning as a whole and specific strategies that can be utilized to create an active learning

environment' and how EAT-PD has 'given me useful strategies to promote better engagement and given me tools to deliver a more effective teaching strategy'. This specific focus on pedagogy and practice when coupled with opportunities to learn 'from other lectures about approaches to student engagement' provided a framework for enhancing practice.

It is likely that hearing about successful implementations from others and experiencing the benefits of active learning themselves increased participants' confidence to implement active learning in their own classes. The qualitative data contains some evidence that the program provided a space to 'try out new theories and techniques each week'. Participants report using tools such as Mentimeter and Jamboard, along with in-class quizzes and peer-instruction. Participants report how adopting these tools impacted student engagement i.e. that they 'found the engagement was better than putting a question to the class and getting blank faces looking back at me', it was 'very helpful to get students to engage more' and how 'the students love seeing the real-time data collection and participation has been very high'. Overall, this qualitative data helps to both support the result that participants are moving towards more learner-centered practices by implementing collaborative approaches for longer durations in the actual classrooms and also helps to explain why EAT-PD may have had this statistically significant impact. Assigning out-of-class work is likely to be related to this impact and faculty are likely to be assigning reading or moving towards flipped classroom approaches to create the space for more active learning in the classroom. It is also likely that with more data this item will become statistically significant.

More recently, academic developers' role in creating 'an environment of trust, in which our colleagues feel supported and valued' has been highlighted (Dransfield et al., 2024). McDonagh & Sanders (2025) explore the building blocks of trust and identified overarching themes which included opportunities for meaningful development, safety, positivity and support, reciprocity/genuine collaboration. We see direct parallels between these themes and the categories useful, course content, peer learning, enjoyable, praise identified in Table 2. Hence relational pedagogy, which views meaningful relationships as fundamental to learning, may also explain the success of EAT-PD.

5.1 Limitations

While the study provides valuable insights into the impact of instructional development on early-career faculty, the reliance on self-reported data is a limitation. The concern is supported by studies that demonstrate a gap between what instructors perceive that they do in the classroom and what is actually observed (Ebert-May et al., 2011) or reported by students (Borda et al., 2020). The response rate declined between the pre- and post-survey instruments (from 51 to 34 participants), which impacts the robustness of the statistical comparisons. We plan to continue to collect data over the coming semesters which should help to address this concern. As this data was collected immediately after the program completed, we do not know if this impact was sustained over the longer term. This is something we also hope to explore in the future. Finally, as the study focused on a single institution and instructional program, the findings may not be generalizable to other contexts or faculty development initiatives.

6 Conclusion

This study highlights the potential of well-designed instructional development initiatives to meaningfully shift early-career faculty toward more active teaching practices. The EAT-PD program demonstrated a statistically significant impact on participants' use of extended collaborative learning. This finding is supported by strong qualitative evidence that faculty gained both the knowledge and practical tools necessary to implement active learning immediately. The data suggests that experiencing active learning strategies and the sharing of

experiences within a peer-supported environment were keys to success and allowed participants to reflect on and reframe their own instructional approaches.

Although the study is limited by self-reported data and declining survey response rates, the findings suggest that programs which combine theory, peer interaction, and practical application are particularly effective in promoting change. Further research could explore long-term impacts on teaching practice and student outcomes, as well as how such programs can be scaled and adapted across institutional contexts.

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